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Relationship Between Teachers' Attitude And Self-Esteem And Class Participation Of Secondary School Students In Makurdi And Guma Local Government Areas Of Benue State

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to investigate the relationship between teachers' attitude and self-esteem and class participation of secondary school students in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State. The researcher adopted the correlational research design. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to sample 380 teachers and students (190 teachers and 190 students) in thirteen secondary schools from a population of 8,334 students and 910 teachers in 21 public secondary schools Makurdi and seven secondary schools in Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The instruments for data collection were Teachers' Attitude Questionnaire (TAQ) adopted from Win and Nwe (2020) and a researcher developed questionnaire titled Students' Psycho-academic Adjustment Questionnaire (SPAQ). The TAQ and SPAQ were subjected to trial testing and their reliability coefficient were analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha. While SPAQ yielded 0.88, TAQ yielded 0.97. The research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). The null hypotheses were also tested using PPMC. It was found that there was significant relationship between teachers' attitude and students' self-esteem in Makurdi and Guma local Government Areas and there was significant relationship between teachers' attitude and students' class participation in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas. it was recommended among others that teachers should avoid attitudes that may negatively affect the self-esteem of secondary school students among other recommendations.

Keywords: Teachers' Attitude, self-esteem, class participation, psycho-academic adjustment, class attendance

INTRODUCTION

It is a fact that education is the crux of every human civilization. As a result, for any nation of the world to develop, the educational development of its populace has to be consciously taken into cognizance. From the foundations of education to tertiary levels, the learner has to be immersed with the learning content in order to bring the needed change to the society. However, since the activities that take place in the formal school setting are relatively different from the informal setting of his or her home, the individual has to adjust both academically and psychologically.

In recent years, the rate of students' failure in external examinations conducted by the West African Examination Council (WAEC) and the National Examination Council (NECO) has not been impressive. In 2023, the WAEC Chief Examiner's report explained that out of 78,419 whose results were successfully processed, more than 41,000 students failed to attain credit passes in Mathematics and three other subjects. The trend continues in 2024 where more than 30% of candidates who sat for the examination failed to attain credit passes in Mathematics, English Language and three other subjects. The persistent decline in students' performance in external examinations may be linked to challenges stemming from students' self-esteem and class participation, which could be influenced by teachers' attitudes.

Teacher attitudes refer to the overall mind-set, feelings and beliefs of the teacher about teaching, their students and the subject they teach. This refers to how they feel about their job and how it directly influences how they act in the classroom. The way teachers engage, support and respond to students can significantly influence their ability to adapt academically and psychologically, ultimately affecting their performance.

Students' psychological and academic adjustment can be influenced by a range of factors, including cognitive, behavioural, emotional responses to academic demands and teachers' attitude. General indicators such as academic engagement, motivation, coping strategies, and social integration shape students' ability to adapt effectively (Adelodun, 2021; Annamaria, Zaharia & Dobrescu, 2025). Among these, self-esteem, self-efficacy and class attendance directly impact academic performance and emotional well-being (Gutiérrez, García & Landeros, 2020). Examining how teachers attitude relate to these indices offers a clearer understanding of their role in students' psycho-academic adjustment.

Teacher attitude is defined as teachers' beliefs, feelings, and predispositions toward students, teaching practices, and the learning environment. It plays a pivotal role in shaping students' psycho-academic adjustment. This term refers to how well students adapt psychologically and academically within the school setting, encompassing emotional well-being, self-concept, motivation and academic performance. Positive teacher attitudes foster emotionally supportive and cognitively stimulating classroom environments that encourage students' growth. Teachers who demonstrate enthusiasm, empathy, fairness, and high expectations tend to enhance students' self-efficacy, engagement, and resilience (Roorda, Koomen, Spilt, & Oort, 2022). These students are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward learning, higher academic achievement, and stronger emotional regulation.

Research shows that teacher attitude is among the vital predictors of student adjustment outcomes. According to Longobardi, Settanni, Lin and Fabris (2021), warm and respectful teacher behaviour significantly contribute to reduction in students' anxiety, improved classroom participation, and better academic outcomes, particularly among younger or more vulnerable learners. In contrast, negative teacher attitudes, such as bias, indifference, or punitive tendencies, can undermine students' psychological security and academic confidence. These attitudes are associated with increased levels of student stress, school avoidance, and academic disengagement (Donohue & Bornman, 2015). Teacher attitude has also in the past been studied in conjunction with psychacademic indices like self-esteem, self-efficacy and class participation.

Students' self-esteem is shaped not only by their own perceptions but also by the responses they receive from their teachers. Responses in the forms of encouragement or rebuke may strengthen or weaken students' self-worth, some of the indices of teacher's positive attitude are ensuring students' emotional support, fair treatment and fostering a comfortable learning environment that improves students' motivation to learn (Magana, 2024; Al-Qadri & Zhao, 2024). Closely related to students' self-esteem is class participation.

Class participation is yet another crucial component of students' academic adjustment. Newmann, Wehlage, and Lamborn (2012) define class participation as a student's psychological investment in learning, demonstrated through efforts to understand or master academic content, skills or crafts.

Class participation can take various forms, including attending lessons, asking questions, responding to the teacher, engaging in peer discussions, and leading classroom conversations under the teacher's guidance. However, participation does not come naturally to all students especially those who experience anxiety or introversion. It is, therefore, the teacher's responsibility to adopt diverse instructional strategies that encourage and facilitate active involvement, ensuring that every student, regardless of personality type, finds a way to engage meaningfully in the learning process.

A teacher's positive and supportive attitude, characterized by encouragement, empathetic listening, and the provision of constructive feedback, significantly fosters student willingness to participate in class, creating a psychologically safe and engaging learning environment (Alqurashi & Pearce, 2024; Wang, Liu, & Chen, 2024; Magana, 2024).

The successful sync of psych-academic indices of self-esteem and class participation with teachers' attitude is a cogent discussion in the teaching and learning process. The present study therefore investigates relationship between teachers' attitude and self-esteem and class participation of secondary school students in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State.

Statement of the Problem

The failure of students to attain requisite credit passes in school subjects in senior secondary school certificate examinations has prompted researchers to seek different solutions. While some scholars attribute these problems to the home environment of students coupled with students' factor, others are of the opinion that this may have emanated from teacher related factors.

Students' Self-esteem and class participation problems in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State have become increasingly evident, particularly among secondary school students. A 2023 report by the Benue State Ministry of Education highlighted rising cases of absenteeism, poor academic performance, and emotional withdrawal among students in both urban and rural schools in Makurdi (Benue State Ministry of Education, 2023). The situation is exacerbated by socio-economic pressures, such as displacement due to herder-farmer crises and poor parental involvement, which contribute to students' anxiety, low self-esteem, and difficulty adjusting to academic demands (UNICEF, 2022). In Guma, some schools reported a growing number of students requiring counseling for trauma-related issues, yet many institutions lack qualified school counselors, leaving students without critical psycho-social support. This inability to cope emotionally and academically creates a cycle of failure, school dropouts, and behavioral problems.

In addition to these challenges, there is growing evidence of negative teacher attitudes in both LGAs, which further hampers students' adjustment and performance. Observations from recent educational assessments conducted in 2024 by the Benue Teaching Service Board reveal that many teachers, especially in underfunded rural schools in Guma, display disinterest, irregular attendance, and use punitive disciplinary methods rather than encouraging classroom engagement (Benue Teaching Service Board, 2024). In Makurdi, while some urban schools benefit from better staffing, overcrowded classrooms and low teacher motivation—often due to unpaid salaries and lack of professional development lead to frustration and neglectful attitudes (Ajuma & Ogwuche, 2024). Students have reported feelings of fear and discouragement, especially when teachers openly express bias, use demeaning language, or fail to provide academic guidance (Oche & Tyopev, 2023). These negative attitudes significantly impact learners' morale and hinder efforts toward holistic academic and psychological development.

The researcher wonders if teachers' attitudes play important roles in the self-esteem and class participation issues amongst students. Teacher attitudes is aligned with core variables like self-esteem and class participation. This study seeks to investigate the relationship between teachers' attitude and self-esteem and class participation of secondary school students in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State.

Objectives of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to ascertain the relationship between teachers' attitude and self-esteem and class participation of secondary school students in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State. The study specifically sought to:

1. Examine the relationship between teachers' attitudes and secondary school students' self-esteem in Makurdi and Guma local government areas.
2. Ascertain the relationship between teachers' attitudes and secondary school students' class participation in Makurdi and Guma local government areas.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

6. What is the relationship between teachers' attitudes and secondary school students' self-esteem in Makurdi and Guma local government areas?
7. What is the relationship between teachers' attitudes and secondary school students' class participation in Makurdi and Guma local government areas?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

4. Self-esteem has no significant relationship with teachers' attitudes in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State
5. Class participation has no significant relationship with teachers' attitudes in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State.

METHODS

This study adopted the correlational design. This type of design sought to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables (Emaikwu, 2015). According to Emaikwu, correlational studies usually indicate the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables.

Correlational design is considered most appropriate for this study because the study sought to provide answers to the relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. The study specifically sought to establish the relationship between teacher attitude and psycho-academic indices like students' self-esteem and self-efficacy, in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State

The population of this study is 9,244 students and teachers (910 teachers and 8334 students) from 21 public secondary schools in Makurdi Local Government and seven schools in Guma Local Government Area. The sample size of this study is 380. The researcher arrived at the sample using Taro Yamen statistical formula for the determination of sample size (1967) (See Appendix H., p. 171). This sample comprised teachers and students in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State. To fulfil the paired observation or paired data assumption criterion for Pearson-Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient, the sample size was purposively split, leading to 190 teachers and 190 students.

In sampling, the researcher first employed the purposive sampling technique to sample 15 schools from the two local government areas. Eleven schools were sampled from Makurdi Local Government Area while four schools were sampled from Guma based on the numbers of schools in the Local Government areas. Also, the researcher also conveniently sampled teachers from the sampled school to ensure that they tally with the sample of 190 teachers. Secondly, the researcher adopted the proportionate stratified sampling technique to get the number of student respondents in each sampled school based on the population of students in the school. This technique aided the researcher to have a fair representation of students in each sampled school based on the population of students.

Thirdly, the researcher used the simple random technique using hat and draw method. This was for sampling of individual respondents. This was undertaken by writing 'Yes' and 'No, in pieces of paper and drop them in a hat. After a thorough shake, students will be asked to pick from the hat.

Students that pick ‘Yes’ were automatically sampled for the study, while students that picked ‘No’ were not counted for the study. This continued until the sample size of 190 was arrived for students. Two instruments were used to collect data for the study. The instruments are: Teachers’ Attitude Questionnaire (TAQ) adopted from Win and Nwe (2020) and a researcher developed questionnaire titled Students’ Psycho-academic Adjustment Questionnaire (SPAQ). The TAQ is a 23-item questionnaire that addressed the variable of teachers’ attitude towards teaching. The response pattern of the instrument is the adapted four-point Liker rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). On the other hand, Students’ Psycho-academic Adjustment Questionnaire (SPAQ) is a 15-item questionnaire with two clusters that cover aspects of student’s psycho-academic adjustment indices. The clusters in the SPAQ range from A-Cand each address indices like self-esteem and class participation.

The instruments were validated by three other research experts; two from Guidance and Counselling and one expert from test and measurement, all in Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. The experts ascertained the face, content and construct validity of the instruments by making some comment to improve the clarity of the instruments.

A trial test was carried out in order to ascertain the reliability of the instruments. Data for this purpose was collected from a school outside the sample but in the area of the study. A total of 20 students and teachers participated in the trail test. Cronbach Alpha was used to analysed the reliability coefficient of the items. Teacher’s Attitude Questionnaire (TAQ) yielded a reliability of 0.9while the clusters in the Students’ Psycho-academic Questionnaire (SPAQ) yielded 0.08 for self-esteem and 0.87, the overall reliability of the instrument was 0.97.

The researcher collected a letter of introduction from the department before proceeding to the schools. Four research assistants were engaged and briefed to assist the researcher in administering the questionnaires. They were properly briefed to understand some of the terms used in the instrument to avoid instrument mortality. The data collected were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between students’ teachers’ attitude and secondary school students’ students’ Self-Esteem in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas?*

Table 1: Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) on the Relationship Between Teachers’ Attitude and Students’ Self- Esteem in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State.

		Teachers Attitude	Students’ Self-Esteem
Teachers’ Attitude	Pearson Correlation	1	.790
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.068
	N	190	190
Students’ Self-Esteem	Pearson Correlation	.790	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
	N	190	190

Table 1 shows there is a strong positive relationship between teacher attitude and students’ self-Esteem in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas (r = .790, n = 380). This result implies that high level of teachers’ attitude is associated with high level of students’ self-esteem.

Research Questions 2: *What is the relationship between teachers' attitudes and secondary school students' class participation in Makurdi and Guma local Government Areas?*

Table 3: Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship between Teachers' Attitude and Secondary School Students' Class Participation in Makurdi and Guma local Government Areas.

		Teachers' attitude	Class Participation
Teachers' attitude	Pearson Correlation	1	.882
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	190	190
Class Participation	Pearson Correlation	.882	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	190	190

Table 3 shows there was a strong positive relationship between teacher attitudes and students' class participation in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State ($r = .882, n = 380$). This result means that high level of teachers' attitude is associated with high level of students' class participation.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Hypothesis One

Students' self-esteem has no significant relationship with teachers' attitudes in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State

Table 4: Pearson Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship between Teachers' Attitude and Secondary School Students' Self- Esteem in Makurdi and Guma LGAs

		Teachers Attitude	Students' Self-Esteem
Students' Self-Esteem	Pearson Correlation	1	.790
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
	N	190	190
Teachers' Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.790	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
	N	190	190

Table 4 shows that $p = 0.003 < 0.05$. Since $p = 0.003$ is less than the alpha value of $.05$, the null hypothesis which states that self-esteem has no significant relationship with teachers' attitudes in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State is rejected. This implies that self-esteem has significant relationship with teachers' attitudes in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State

Hypotheses Two

Class participation has no significant relationship with teachers' attitudes in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State.

Table 6: Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship between Teachers' Attitude and Secondary School Students' Class Participation in Makurdi and Guma LGAs

		Teachers' attitude	Class Participation
Teachers' attitude	Pearson Correlation	1	.882
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	190	190
Class Participation	Pearson Correlation	.882	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	190	190

Table 6 presents $p. 0.000 < 0.05$. Since $p. 0.000$ is less than the alpha of 0.05 , the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between teachers' attitude and students' class participation in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas is rejected. This result means that class participation has significant relationship with teachers' attitudes in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The following discussions are in line with the findings of the present study

The first finding of the study revealed that teachers' attitude has significant relationship with students' self-esteem in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State. This finding establishes the importance of teacher attitude when considering issues around students' self-esteem. As a psychological index that is influenced by social interaction, self-esteem, often termed the belief in oneself, could be reinvigorated by teachers' attitudes within and outside the confine of the classroom. The finding could be particularly due to the role the teacher plays in the class as an individual that encourages students to believe in themselves. The finding agrees with Prihadi, Ismail and Jamil (2017) who carried out a study on students' self-esteem and their perception of teacher attitude in Bangladesh and found that students' perception of teacher attitude does significantly influence their self-esteem. The finding however disagrees with Kashani, Dahar and Parvee (2023) who investigated impact of teachers' attitude on self-esteem of students in India and found that teacher's attitude has no significant impact on students' self-esteem.

The second finding of the study revealed that teachers' attitude has significant relationship with students' class participation in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State. This finding could be due to the fact that a students' willingness to participate in class discussion is due to how the teacher conducts his or herself in the classroom. As a result, a teacher who uses students-friendly approaches to encourage students to participate actively during a lesson may get better results than the one who uses aggressive or less student-friendly approaches. Either way, teacher attitude determines if students eventually participate in the lesson. The finding agrees with Ahmad and Batool (2018) who conducted a quantitative study to examine the relationship between teachers' behavior and student participation in classroom discussions among secondary school students in Pakistan and found a moderately strong positive correlation between supportive teacher behavior and active student participation. The study also agrees with Bibi, Khan and Ali (2023) conducted an insightful study in Pakistan to explore secondary school students' perceptions of teacher behaviours and their influence on maintaining discipline and encouraging participation in classroom settings and found that teacher behaviour significantly influence students' class participation.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated relationship between teachers' attitude and self-esteem and class participation of secondary school students in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas of Benue State. Based on the result from empirical data, the study concludes that there is significant relationship between teacher attitudes and self-esteem and class participation of secondary school students in Makurdi and Guma Local Government Areas.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are recommended based on the findings of this study:

1. Teachers should avoid attitudes that may negatively affect the self-esteem of secondary school students.
2. Teachers should promote students' class participation by demonstrating positive attitudes during teaching and learning sessions.

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